

26 August 2020

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Notice of grant for your innovation patent

CHRISTO ANANTH

Department of Electronics and
Communication Engineering
St.Mother Theresa Engineering College
Thoothukudi Tamil Nadu
India

Patent number	2020101682
Patentee name	CHRISTO ANANTH, Praghash K, Niha K, Narendran S, Marshiana D, Nanjesh BR, Ahila A, G.Victor Emmanuel, D. Angeline Ranjithamani, Selina Annie Retna V
Your reference	CHRISTO2

Your progress

- Filed**
Application is filed
- Acceptance and Grant**
Application is accepted and patent granted
- Examination**
Patent is being examined
- Certification**
Patent is certified
(patent is now enforceable)
- Renewal**
Renewal fees required to maintain patent
(fees are due annually- please refer to the 'paid to' date in AusPat for your next due date)

Dear Patentee,

The granting of your application has been processed. The date of grant is 26 August 2020 and the Certificate of Grant is enclosed.

What will happen next

- The granted patent number will be published in the next available [Australian Official Journal of Patents](#).
- Your first renewal fee payment, being for the 2nd year anniversary, is due on 5 August 2022.

What you can do

- **Request examination** – this is optional and you can request examination at any time during the term of your patent. The fee is currently \$500.

Things to be aware of

- Your patent cannot be legally enforced until it is certified through examination.
- If examination is requested and your patent does not meet the requirements for certification, your patent will cease.
- The term of your innovation patent is 8 years from the date of the patent (5 August 2020).

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Your reference CHRISTO2

- To maintain your innovation patent you have to pay annual renewal fees. The fee can be paid up to 6 months after 5 August 2022 provided it is accompanied by the required late payment fee. Your patent will cease if renewal fees are not paid.

Details of your patent can be viewed on [AusPat](#), our Australian patent search database.

Yours sincerely,

IP Australia

Australian Government

IP Australia

CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2020101682

The Commissioner of Patents has granted the above patent on 26 August 2020, and certifies that the below particulars have been registered in the Register of Patents.

Name and address of patentee(s):

CHRISTO ANANTH of Department of Electronics and, Communication Engineering, St.Mother Theresa Engineering College Thoothukudi Tamil Nadu India

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Narendran S of Research Scholar, Electronics, and Communication Engineering SRM Institute of Science and Technology Chennai Tamil Nadu India

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Selina Annie Retna V of PG Student, Department of Computer Science and, Engineering Francis Xavier Engineering College Tamil Nadu India

Title of invention:

ELECTROCARDIOGRAM REMOTE MONITORING SYSTEM BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Name of inventor(s):

ANANTH, CHRISTO; K., Praghash; K., Niha; S., Narendran; D., Marshiana; BR, Nanjesh; A., Ahila; Emmanuel, G.Victor; Ranjithamani, D. Angeline and Annie Retna V., Selina

Term of Patent:

Eight years from 5 August 2020

Dated this 26th day of August 2020

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to this IP Right.

Australian Government

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CERTIFICATE OF GRANT INNOVATION PATENT

Patent number: 2020101682

NOTE: This Innovation Patent cannot be enforced unless and until it has been examined by the Commissioner of Patents and a Certificate of Examination has been issued. See sections 120(1A) and 129A of the Patents Act 1990, set out on the reverse of this document.

Dated this 26th day of August 2020

Commissioner of Patents

PATENTS ACT 1990

The Australian Patents Register is the official record and should be referred to for the full details pertaining to this IP Right.

